

Hidradenocarcinoma a rare case and challenging diagnosis

Authors:

Rachneet Kaur¹, Dr. Anil Luther², Dr. Preethi Anni Mercy Paul³

¹MBBS Student, Christian Medical College Ludhiana

²Professor, Department of general Surgery, Christian Medical College Ludhiana

³Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Christian Medical College Ludhiana

Corresponding Author:

Rachneet Kaur

MBBS Student, Christian Medical College Ludhiana

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ABSTRACT:

Hidradenocarcinoma is a rare malignant adnexal tumor arising from eccrine sweat glands, with diagnostic and therapeutic challenges due to its benign clinical appearance and limited literature on standardized management. We report the case of a 66-year-old male who presented with a painless, progressively enlarging axillary swelling initially suspected to be hidradenitis suppurativa. Surgical excision followed by histopathological and immunohistochemical evaluation confirmed the diagnosis of hidradenocarcinoma. This case underscores the importance of considering a broad differential diagnosis when evaluating atypical cutaneous lesions, as they may be malignant despite appearing benign. Through this report, we aim to contribute to the limited literature on hidradenocarcinoma and support the development of more effective management strategies for this rare condition.

Keywords: *Hidradenoma, Hidradenitis Suppurative, Sweat Gland Neoplasm, Hidradenocarcinoma*

INTRODUCTION:

Hidradenocarcinoma is an uncommon malignant tumor accounting for less than 0.001% of all cancers. It is also referred to by several other names, such as clear cell eccrine carcinoma, malignant nodular hidradenoma, and malignant clear cell acrospiroma, based on histochemical and electron microscopy findings.[1] It arises from the intradermal ductal epithelium of eccrine sweat glands and typically develops de novo, although it can also arise from a benign hidradenoma. (2) The tumor commonly presents as a single, firm, asymptomatic intradermal nodule ranging from 1 to 5 cm, often covered by intact or occasionally ulcerated lesions that are purple, pink, or blue in color. The differential diagnosis of hidradenocarcinoma is challenging due to its benign appearance, which resembles other skin tumors. (3) Diagnosis relies on histological and immunohistochemical evaluation. (4) Given its rarity, the management of hidradenocarcinoma is not well established in the literature. The use of adjuvant chemotherapy and radiation remains controversial, and further studies are needed to develop a comprehensive treatment approach beyond wide excision. (5) This case

report details a patient with hidradenocarcinoma of the left axilla.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 66-year-old married gentleman from Ludhiana presented to the general surgery outpatient department with chief complaints of swelling in the left axillary region for the past 8-9 months. The patient had no known comorbidities.

Swelling began insidiously approximately 8-9 months ago and progressively increased in size, particularly over the last 1-2 months, developing a shiny reddish hue. Notably, the patient reported no pain, fever, or active pus discharge, and did not experience any weight loss or similar lesions elsewhere on his body. Although there was initially no history of pus discharge or bleeding, in the last 1-2 months, he noticed staining of his clothing with spots of blood and pus.

The patient had no clinically significant past medical or surgical history, and there were no notable findings in his family history. He was a long-term tobacco chewer.

General Physical Examination:

The patient was conscious, alert, and well-oriented to time, place, and person. The results of general physical examination are listed in Table 1.1

BMI	27.9
BP	140/70 mmHg (in sitting position)
Pulse Rate	92/ min with normal characteristics
Oxygen saturation	98%
Temperature	Afebrile
Pallor/ Icterus / Cyanosis/ Clubbing / General lymphadenopathy / Edema	Absent

Upon inspection of the left axillary region, a 2.0 x 3.0 x 2.0 cm elongated mass with a central pus point and a pale tip was observed (Fig 1.1 A and 1.1 B). On palpation, the mass was noted to be firm, non-tender, non-pulsatile, and fixed to the skin. Notably, lymph nodes were non-palpable. Based on the initial clinical features, the patient was diagnosed with Hidradenitis suppurativa.

Fig. 1.1 A

Fig 1.1 B

Ultrasound reports revealed a well-defined, lobulated, with polypoidal outgrowth, mixed solid - cystic lesion measuring 2.2x 1.2x1.7 cm was noted in the subcutaneous plane of the left axillary region. Significant internal vascularity was noted having a high resistive index up to 1.1. No evidence of any internal calcification or deeper extension of the lesion was noted. These findings were suggestive of neoplastic/inflammatory aetiology. FNAC / Histopathological correlation was advised.

Management and Diagnosis:

Patient underwent excision and biopsy of left axillary growth under general anaesthesia. The mass was sent for biopsy reports. A wide excisional margin of 2-2.5 cm

was taken for the surgery. Operative findings revealed a polypoidal swelling of approximately 4.0 x 3.0 cm in the left axillary region.

Section sent for biopsy reports showed a skin adnexal tumour comprising of epithelial cells arranged in papillae, cribriform pattern, variable sized cystic spaces and few strands. The cells had moderately pleomorphic vesicular nuclei with prominent 1-2 nucleoli, irregular nuclear margins, and a moderate amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm. Scattered mitotic figures were also seen. The tumour was reaching up to the epidermis at places. Some areas showed irregular glands infiltrating into dermis. Lymphovascular invasion was also present. The underlying base was also found to be free of tumour. (Fig 1.2 A, 1.2B, 1.2C, 1.2D)

Figure 1.2

Figure 1: Microphotographs from the left axillary skin, showing A) a skin adnexal tumour in the dermis arranged in papillae, tubules, cribriform and tubular patterns, 40x, B) prominent cribriform pattern, 100x; C) lymphatic invasion identified within the dermal lymphatics (arrows), 400x; D) on higher magnification, the tumour cells showed moderate nuclear enlargement with prominent nucleoli and moderate amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm, 400x; hematoxylin and eosin. Immunohistochemistry showing A) diffuse positivity for CK7, 400x; B) diffuse strong positivity for EMA, 400x; C) focal nuclear reactivity for androgen receptor, 400x; and D) a Ki67 proliferative index of approximately 20-30%, 400x; diaminobenzidine chromogen.

Features in the biopsy report of left axilla were suggestive of HIDRADENOMA PAPILLIFERUM with suspicious foci of malignant change into adenocarcinoma.

Immunohistochemistry reports revealed features which were suggestive of HIDRADENOCARCINOMA in the left axilla. There was a strong positivity of CK7 and EMA in the tumour cells. Strong focal positivity of androgen receptor (AR), pCEA in the tumour cells. SMA was negative in the tumour cells. Ki67 was approximately 20- 30 %. (Fig 1.3 A, 1.3 B, 1.3 C, 1.3 D)

Figure 1.3

The patient was finally diagnosed with HIDRADENOCARCINOMA. A PET scan was planned to check for residuals, however, there was loss of follow up from the patient.

SUMMARY:

A 66-year-old gentleman with no known comorbid illness presented to the OPD with complaints of a painless, gradually progressive swelling in the left axilla for the past 8-9 months. The patient was initially clinically diagnosed with Hidradenitis suppurativa. Surgical excision with a wide excisional margin, and biopsy of the swelling were done. Histopathological biopsy reports suspected it to be a case of Hidradenoma papilliferum. Immunohistochemistry reports later confirmed it to be Hidradenocarcinoma of the left axillae.

DISCUSSION:

Hidradenocarcinoma is a rare tumor of the sweat glands, typically affecting individuals in their fifth to seventh decades of life. It most commonly occurs on the skin of the head, neck, or extremities. (6) The tumor can present with a wide range of histomorphologic features, from low to high grade. Diagnosing low-grade hidradenocarcinoma can be challenging and may be confused with benign hidradenomas, especially in superficial or partial tissue samples. (7) Due to its rarity and potential for aggressive behavior, early and accurate diagnosis is essential for determining the best treatment approach and improving patient outcomes. (8) Currently, there are no established treatment guidelines, particularly for patients with nodal involvement. (9) However, based on available literature, wide local excision and sentinel lymph node biopsy are the most commonly employed initial treatment strategies. (10)

CONCLUSION:

Hidradenocarcinoma is a rare malignancy which can be difficult to diagnose and manage because its presentation is usually subtle and often mimics benign conditions.

Diagnosis is made through histopathological examination and imaging studies. Surgical excision remains the primary treatment, although the role of adjuvant therapies such as radiation or chemotherapy is still under investigation. Further research into its pathogenesis, treatment options, and long-term prognosis is necessary to enhance the understanding and management of this challenging neoplasm.

FINANCIAL IMPLICATIONS: None

Conflicts Of Interest: None

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